

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It gives me great pleasure to announce the eighth regular issue of 2023. In this issue, five papers by 24 authors from nine countries cover various topical aspects of computer science. In an ongoing effort to further strengthen our journal, I would like to expand the editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a strong publication record, you are welcome to apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and trends.

As always, I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research and the editorial board for their extremely valuable review effort and suggestions for improvements. These contributions, together with the generous support of the consortium members, sustain the quality of our journal.

As we want to secure the financial support also for the years to come, we are looking for institutions and libraries to financially support our diamond open access journal as consortium members, who will then benefit from the research community, international visibility, and the opportunity to manage special issues and focused topics within the journal. Please think about the possibility of such financial participation of your institution, we would be very grateful for any kind of support.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce the following 5 accepted articles: In a collaborative research effort between Jordan and Qatar, Ahmad Abusukhon, Ala Al-Fuqaha and Belal Hawashin present their technique for detecting underground water pipeline leakage based on an Internet of Things approach. In another collaboration between researchers from Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina, Ani Grubišić, Slavomir Stankov, Branko Žitko, Ines Šarić-Grgić, Angelina Gašpar, Emil Brajković, and Daniel Vasić describe and evaluate the performance of a semi-automatic authoring tool for knowledge extraction in the AC&NL Tutor and discuss strengths and weaknesses. Also in a collaboration between researchers from the United States and United Arab Emirates, Longhao Li, Taieb Znati, and Rami Melhem propose an energy-aware fault-tolerance model for silent error detection and mitigation in heterogeneous extreme-scale computing environments, referred to diffReplication, which is associated with one replica that executes at the same rate as the main process, and one diffReplica that is executed at a fraction of the execution rate of the main process. In a collaboration between researchers from China and Japan, Xiaojuan Liao, Hui Zhang, Miyuki Koshimura, Rong Huang, and Fagen Li propose in their paper an optimized strategy for solving restricted preemptive scheduling on parallel machines applying Partial Maximum Satisfiability (PMS), an optimized version of a Boolean Satisfiability (SAT) solver. Finally, in a collaboration between researchers from South Korea and the USA, Jaeyoung Yang, Sooin Kim, Sangwoo

Lee, Won-gyum Kim, Donghoon Kim, and Doosung Hwang aim in their paper to establish a binary classification method for distinguishing copyrighted and non-copyrighted images by introducing a deep hashing model for an image authentication system, which uses deep learning-based perceptual hashing.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

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